

Assessment of the Effectiveness of Peer Assisted Learning in Radiography Training Among Radiography Students in University Of Maiduguri

*¹Abubakar, G. Mathew

²Qasim, A. Abatcha

³Augustine Uzoma Madu: *Orcid: 0000-0002-6917-9008*

⁴Zamdai, A. Esther

^{1, 2, 4} Department of Medical Radiography, Faculty of Allied Health Sciences, University of Maiduguri, Borno State

³ Dept. Library and Information Science. University of Maiduguri

*Corresponding author: mattosky@unimaid.edu.ng (+2348066740058)

Abstract

To evaluate the impact of Peer Assisted Learning (PAL) on students' academic performance in radiography, and determine students' perceptions of PAL as a learning method. Also, to compare PAL with traditional teaching methods in radiography education. A non-experimental cross-sectional study was carried out among 169 Radiography students at UNIMAID. Demographics and perceptions were organized and then analyzed using the SPSS version 25. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were obtained. The results showed that 79.1% of respondents agreed that PAL helped them understand complex topics, and 73.5% found it beneficial in preparing for exams. This supports the notion that PAL provides a conducive learning environment that complements traditional teaching. The inferential statistical analysis also confirmed the significance of students' positive perceptions toward PAL. The majority acknowledged PAL as a flexible and student-friendly method that promotes engagement and learning through collaboration. However, the opinion revealed the importance of traditional method as complimentary to PAL. The study concludes that Peer-Assisted Learning (PAL) is an effective educational strategy in radiography training. It positively influences academic performance, promotes collaboration, and enhance confidence. PAL provides a platform for peer interaction, which promotes mutual learning and skill development. In resource-constrained settings such as the University of Maiduguri, PAL is particularly valuable in bridging the gap caused by limited teaching staff and inadequate practical facilities.

Key words: *PAL: Peer-Assisted Learning, Traditional learning, Radiography, University of Maiduguri*

Introduction

Medical education demands effective learning strategies to ensure students grasp complex concepts, develop critical thinking skills, and become competent professionals. One such strategy is Peer-Assisted Learning (PAL), a structured approach where students at similar or different academic levels support each other's learning. PAL fosters collaboration, improves knowledge retention, and enhances confidence among learners. Peer-Assisted Learning (PAL) has been described by Topping as 'people from similar social groupings, who are not professional teachers helping each other to learn, and learning themselves by teaching. Topping (1996)

Previous studies have demonstrated the positive impact of PAL in various medical disciplines. For example, Clarissa *et al.* (2022) highlighted its role in enhancing academic performance of students engaging in PAL in contrast to those who weren't. Yet, the effectiveness of such informal peer-assisted strategies in radiography training, particularly in the Nigerian context, remains underexplored.

Also, the PAL programme at Nova Southeastern University Dr. Kiran C. Patel College of Allopathic Medicine provided first-year medical students with educational sessions related to their curriculum, led by second-year medical students. The goal of this study was to determine the efficacy of PAL in promoting wellness and enhancing knowledge. After pre and post program surveys, the results of the study showed Thirty-eight out of 51 first-year medical students responded to the pre-programme survey (response rate 75%) and 23 out of 51 responded to the post-programme survey (response rate 45%). A majority of respondents from the pre-survey believed that PAL would provide them with tools necessary to be successful (Williams *et al.*, 2021)

In radiography training, where both theoretical knowledge and practical skills are essential, PAL has gained attention as a complementary learning method. Traditional lecture-based teaching methods sometimes struggle to provide individualized attention, making PAL an attractive alternative. Studies have shown that PAL can improve academic performance, enhance communication skills, and encourage active participation in learning.

At the University of Maiduguri, radiography students face challenges such as limited access to well-equipped skills labs, making hands-on training less effective. While faculty members are available, the lack of sufficient practical training facilities can hinder students' ability to develop essential radiographic skills. PAL could help bridge this gap by allowing senior students to guide junior ones through complex topics and clinical skills. However, its effectiveness in this setting has not been thoroughly assessed. This study, therefore, aims to evaluate the effectiveness of informal PAL strategies in radiography training at the University of Maiduguri, focusing on their influence on academic performance, clinical confidence, and engagement among students.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Radiography education requires the integration of rigorous theoretical knowledge with the precise development of clinical and technical competencies. Although Peer-Assisted Learning (PAL) has been widely recognised as an effective pedagogical strategy in medical and allied health education, its structured implementation and measurable impact within radiography training at the University of Maiduguri remain largely unexplored. While students frequently engage in informal peer interactions to clarify concepts and practice clinical skills, these activities occur without systematic coordination, monitoring, or empirical evaluation.

Consequently, there is insufficient evidence to determine whether PAL meaningfully improves academic performance, strengthens clinical competence, or enhances students' confidence in radiographic practice within this context. The absence of context-specific assessment creates a gap in pedagogical knowledge and limits informed decision-making regarding curriculum design and instructional innovation in the Department of Medical Radiography. In light of these gaps, there is a clear need to assess the effectiveness of peer-assisted learning among radiography students at

the University of Maiduguri. These observed problems aligns those outlined by pioneer studies on PAL by Lincoln and McAlister (1993) and (Secomb, 2008).

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To determine students' participation in PAL
2. The frequency of students engage in PAL
3. To evaluate the impact of PAL on students' academic performance in radiography.
4. To determine students' perceptions of PAL as a learning method.
5. To compare PAL with traditional teaching methods in radiography education.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Peer-Assisted Learning (PAL) is a collaborative pedagogical approach in which students support one another's learning through structured or informal academic interactions. Widely applied in health sciences education, PAL complements conventional instruction by fostering active engagement in both theoretical understanding and clinical skill acquisition (Topping, 1996). Its relevance to radiography training lies in the discipline's dual emphasis on conceptual knowledge and procedural competence.

The theoretical grounding of PAL is anchored in several complementary learning theories. Albert Bandura's Social Learning Theory (1977) posits that learning occurs through observation, modeling, and social interaction. In radiography education, students observe peers demonstrate imaging techniques and clinical procedures, reinforcing skill acquisition through imitation and feedback. Similarly, Lev Vygotsky's concept of the Zone of Proximal Development (1978) explains how learners achieve higher levels of competence when guided by more knowledgeable peers. Within PAL frameworks, senior students scaffold junior colleagues' understanding, gradually transferring responsibility as competence increases an approach particularly suited to clinically intensive disciplines.

The Cognitive Apprenticeship Model proposed by Allan Collins, John Seely Brown, and Susan Newman (2018) further supports PAL by emphasizing situated learning through mentorship, guided practice, and reflective dialogue. In this model, learners alternate between roles as apprentices and peer mentors, thereby deepening procedural knowledge and professional competence. Complementing these perspectives, Jean Piaget's Constructivist Learning Theory (1950s) asserts that knowledge is actively constructed through interaction and experience. PAL facilitates this process by encouraging dialogue, problem-solving, and collaborative reflection, all of which promote deeper cognitive processing.

Collectively, these theoretical perspectives justify PAL as an effective strategy for enhancing academic performance, clinical confidence, and learner engagement in radiography training. This study therefore draws on these theoretical foundations to assess the effectiveness of peer-assisted learning in improving educational outcomes among radiography students at the University of Maiduguri.

A growing body of global research provides empirical support for the effectiveness of Peer-Assisted Learning (PAL) in health professions education, highlighting its academic, clinical, and professional benefits (Feng et al., 2024; Jawhari et al., 2021; Røe et al., 2025). Evidence consistently demonstrates that PAL enhances examination performance, clinical competence, communication skills, and learner satisfaction across medical and allied health disciplines.

For instance, Clarissa *et al.* (2022) reported that medical students who participated in PAL achieved significantly better academic outcomes than those who did not, with the greatest benefits observed during clinical training and practical skill development. Similarly, a meta-analysis by Burgess et al. (2014) found that students engaged in PAL performed significantly better in examinations compared to peers relying solely on lecture-based instruction. Chiegeiro et al. (2025), found that peer teaching significantly improved students' academic performance in anatomy compared to the traditional lecture method.

Within radiography and medical imaging education, empirical findings reinforce these outcomes. Markowski et al. (2021) examined peer mentorship during clinical placements for radiography students and found notable improvements in clinical competency, confidence, and teamwork skills. Cornock and McKenna (2012) similarly observed that PAL strengthened students' ability to interpret radiographic images and apply theoretical knowledge to real-world clinical scenarios. In a more recent study, Meertens (2016) reported that PALS demonstrated to be an effective initiative within the undergraduate programme and will be continued into the future. Similarly, Elshami et al., (2020) investigated radiography students' perceptions of a PAL programme implemented in a second-year programme. Using 13 Likert-scale questions administered to 28 students, with a response rate of 92.8%, data were analysed using descriptive statistics and logistic regression analysis. The study showed a high level of acceptance (79.9%–92.3%) across all items, indicating a positive understanding of PAL. The logistic regression analysis identified two key factors influencing acceptance, and the overall results indicated that PAL improved students' learning experiences and supported exam preparation.

Complementing these findings, Chiegeiro et al., (2025) revealed that students in the peer-taught group demonstrated higher achievement and a larger proportion scored above 60% compared with the control group, indicating that peer teaching was more effective in enhancing academic performance in anatomy. While the traditional lecture group showed some improvement, it was not statistically significant, highlighting the stronger impact of the peer teaching approach. The findings suggest that engaging students actively through peer instruction increases interest and understanding of anatomy, and that both methods can enhance learning if properly applied; however, peer teaching showed greater academic gains in this setting.

Regional evidence also supports the relevance of PAL in resource-constrained contexts. Oladipo and Ayoola (2018) in a Nigerian study among nursing students, identified a positive correlation between peer teaching and academic performance. Although not radiography-specific, the findings demonstrate PAL's adaptability and effectiveness within healthcare education systems facing infrastructural and faculty limitations.

Collectively, these empirical studies affirm that PAL functions as an effective complement to traditional instruction by bridging the gap between theory and practice, enhancing clinical reasoning, and promoting collaborative professional skills. However, despite substantial international evidence, there remains limited research examining the effectiveness of informal PAL strategies within radiography programmes in Nigerian universities. This contextual gap underscores the need for localised investigation into how peer-assisted learning influences academic performance, clinical competence, and student confidence in radiography training environments characterised by unique logistical and instructional challenges.

Beyond knowledge acquisition, PAL has been associated with the development of higher-order cognitive skills while students' perceptions of teaching strategies are essential for enhancing educational quality. Yet limited evidence exists regarding views on lectures and peer-assisted learning (PAL) among biomedical and allied health students. Based on the above, Oppong et al., (2024) conducted a cross-sectional study surveyed of 213 students (levels 200–400) at the University of Ghana using an adopted perceptions questionnaire. Data were analysed using mean scores, one-way ANOVA, and independent sample t-tests. PAL received a higher global rating (mean 4.1, SD 0.8) than lectures (mean 3.5, SD 0.8; $p < 0.001$). No significant differences were found across study levels. Female students reported more positive perceptions of PAL, while perceptions of lectures were similarly positive among both genders. Vermunt and Verloop (1999) further argued that the effectiveness of PAL depends on the quality of peer interaction, particularly when knowledgeable senior students mentor junior learners. Such guided interaction facilitates the transfer of tacit clinical knowledge, especially in contexts where faculty supervision may be limited.

Student perceptions and acceptance significantly influence the success of PAL initiatives. Loke and Chow (2007) observed that students value the approachability of peer tutors in clinical environments, noting reduced anxiety and greater participation. Similarly, AlShareef et al., (2019) on Perceptions of reciprocal peer teaching among medical students as learners and as Tutors indicate that 34.5% of learners agreed that peer-tutoring was the most effective method of clinical teaching and 30.3% disagreed. More students reported that peer-led seminars did not prepare them for their exams (38.4%) compared to those who reported it did (27.9%). More than 40% of participants reported the tutors were approachable, created a welcoming learning environment and provided targeted information. These findings indicate that structured orientation and tutor readiness are critical determinants of effective PAL implementation.

Within radiography specifically, emerging evidence supports the pedagogical value of peer learning, while Cornock and McKenna (2020) reported improvements in technical competence, teamwork, and communication skills—attributes essential for collaborative radiographic practice. Ross and Cameron (2007) further linked PAL participation to heightened self-confidence in practical skills, and Nestel and Kidd (2013) highlighted its role in facilitating the transition from theoretical instruction to clinical application. Earlier work by Nestel and Kidd (2005) also emphasized reciprocal benefits, whereby senior students consolidate knowledge while junior learners receive simplified, contextually relevant guidance.

Engagement and motivation represent additional conceptual strengths of PAL. Kassab et al. (2006) noted that informal peer-learning environments foster active participation and open communication. Engels et al., (2021) found that PAL enhances intrinsic motivation and positive learning attitudes among health science students, while Bosch et al. (2014) reported increased interest in both theoretical and practical components of radiography education through active peer involvement. Topping (2005) similarly suggested that immediate, relatable feedback from peers promotes sustained motivation and academic resilience.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a cross-sectional research design to assess the effectiveness of peer-assisted learning among undergraduate radiography students at the University of Maiduguri. Data were collected from a primary source using a structured online questionnaire developed through Google Forms. The target population comprised all undergraduate students in the Department of Radiography, with eligibility limited to students in 200, 300, 400, and 500 levels, while 100-level students were excluded due to limited exposure to core professional and clinical courses.

A sample size of 196 respondents was determined using Yamane’s formula for sample size estimation. Participants were selected using a convenience non-probability sampling technique, based on availability and willingness to participate. Data collected were analysed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies and percentages, were employed to summarise respondents’ characteristics and responses. Inferential analysis was conducted using binomial tests to examine significant differences and relationships among key variables. Informed consent was secured from all participants prior to data collection, and confidentiality and voluntary participation were ensured throughout the study.

RESULT

7.1 Demographic Information

Table 1: Demographic Information

Question	Response Options	Frequency	Percentage
Level	200 Level	45	23.0%
	300 Level	64	32.7%
	400 Level	52	26.5%
	500 Level	35	17.9%
Gender	Male	123	62.8%
	Female	73	37.2%

The demographic profile shows that the majority of respondents were in 300 Level with 64 students (32.7%), followed by 200 Level with 45 students (23.0%), 400 Level with 52 students (26.5%), and 500 Level with 35 students (17.9%). This distribution reflects a balanced representation across levels, though mid-level students participated more actively in the study. In terms of gender, male respondents dominated with 123 (62.8%) compared to females with 73 (37.2%).

Students' Participation in PAL

Table 2: Students participation in PAL

Table with 4 columns: Question, Yes, No, Maybe. Row: Have you participated in PAL? (115/58.7%, 60/30.6%, 21/10.7%)

The Students participation in PAL (table 2) show that a majority 115 (58.7%) have participated in PAL, indicating relatively high engagement in the learning. However, 60(30.6%) reported no participation, while 21(10.7%) were uncertain about their involvement.

Students' Frequency of Engagement in PAL

Table 3: Frequency of Students' engagement in PAL

Table with 5 columns: Question, Daily, Weekly, Occasionally, Never. Row: How often do you engage in PAL? (70/35.7%, 56/28.6%, 50/25.5%, 20/10.2%)

The findings on students' engagement in pal reveal that a majority of respondents participated in peer-assisted learning either daily (35.7%) or weekly (28.6%). THIS suggests frequent participation in peer-learning activities. A smaller proportion reported occasional engagement (25.5%), while only 10.2% indicated that they never participated in PAL activities.

Impact of Pal on Academic Performance

Table 4: Impact of PAL on Academic Performance

Table with 3 columns: Statement, True, False. Rows: PAL helps me understand complex topics, PAL has improved my academic performance, I feel more confident academically due to PAL, PAL sessions help me prepare for tests and exams, PAL supports my understanding better than self-study alone.

The findings in table 4 strongly support the positive academic influence of PAL. A total of 155 students (79.1%) agreed that PAL helps them understand complex topics, while 41 (20.9%) disagreed. Similarly, 127 (64.8%) indicated that PAL has improved their academic performance compared to 69 (35.2%) who did not share this view.

Students' Perception of PAL

Table 5: Perception of PAL

Table with 3 columns: Statement, Response, Frequency. Rows include statements like 'PAL makes learning more interactive and engaging' with corresponding counts and percentages.

Regarding students perceptions of PAL., majority of 153 (78.1%) believed that PAL makes learning more interactive and engaging, while 43 (21.9%) did not. Learning comfort was also evident, as 132 (67.3%) felt comfortable learning from fellow students, whereas 64 (32.7%) did not.

PAL VS Traditional Teaching Methods

Table 6: PAL vs. Traditional Teaching Methods

Table with 3 columns: Statement, True, False. Rows include statements like 'PAL helps me ask questions I may hesitate to ask in class' with counts and percentages.

The comparative analysis of PAL and traditional teaching methods revealed complementary strengths. A total of 159 students (81.1%) reported that PAL helps them ask questions they may hesitate to ask in class, while 37 (18.9%) did not.

To determine whether the student preferences and perceptions reported in Table 7 were statistically significant or unlikely to have occurred by chance, a Binomial Tests were conducted. The null hypothesis for each test stated that the proportion of "True" responses was equal to 0.5 (50%), indicating no clear majority opinion.

in class, 159 out of 196 students (81.1%) responded True, and the result was highly significant (p < .001). This indicates strong support for PAL in promoting open academic interaction. Similarly, 63.3% of students agreed that they learn better through PAL than traditional lectures (p = .001), suggesting a statistically significant preference for PAL in facilitating learning. Interestingly, 69.4% also agreed that traditional lectures provide more structure than PAL (p < .001), indicating that students still recognise the organisational strengths of the traditional method. Furthermore, 76.0% agreed that PAL is more flexible and student-friendly (p < .001), while 70.9% agreed that PAL and traditional teaching complement each other (p < .001). Overall, the findings suggest that students significantly favour PAL for interaction, flexibility, and enhanced learning, while also acknowledging the structural benefits of traditional lectures. The acceptance of all statements indicates that both methods have distinct strengths and are perceived as complementary rather than mutually exclusive.

Table 7: Results of Binomial Tests for PAL vs. Traditional Methods

Table with 7 columns: Statement, N, True Responses (n), Proportion (p), Test Proportion, p-value, Decision. Rows include statements like 'PAL helps me ask questions I may hesitate to ask in class' and 'I learn better through PAL than traditional lectures'.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study revealed that Peer-Assisted Learning (PAL) has a significant positive impact on radiography students at the University of Maiduguri. The high participation rate and positive perceptions demonstrate that PAL enhances academic performance, promotes understanding of complex topics, and builds student confidence. This aligns with earlier studies by Ten Cate and Durning (2007) and Chiegeiro et al., (2025), which emphasized PAL’s effectiveness in fostering collaboration and knowledge retention in medical education. The results showed that 79.1% of respondents agreed that PAL helped them understand complex topics, and 73.5% found it beneficial in preparing for exams. This supports the notion that PAL provides a conducive learning environment that complements traditional teaching. The inferential statistical analysis also confirmed the significance of students’ positive perceptions toward PAL. The majority acknowledged PAL as a flexible and student-friendly method that promotes engagement and learning through collaboration. Additionally, the findings indicate that PAL encourages students to ask questions they might hesitate to ask in traditional classes, thereby improving communication and reducing anxiety. This is consistent with the findings of Loke and Chow (2007), who noted that PAL fosters a non-intimidating environment where students feel free to interact. However, while students valued PAL for its flexibility, they also recognized the

structured advantage of traditional lectures. This suggests that both PAL and conventional methods should coexist as complementary strategies to achieve optimal learning outcomes.

For the comparison, the binomial tests revealed that for all five statements, the proportion of "True" responses was statistically significantly different from 50% (all $p \leq .001$). This allows for the rejection of the null hypothesis in each case. The inferential analysis confirms that the perceptions reported descriptively are not merely anecdotal but represent statistically significant preferences within the student population. The results provide quantitative evidence that PAL is significantly preferred for its interactive and flexible nature, while traditional lectures are significantly valued for their structure. Crucially, there is significant consensus that the two approaches are complementary.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that Peer-Assisted Learning (PAL) is an effective educational strategy in radiography training. It positively influences academic performance, promotes collaboration, enhances confidence, and complements traditional methods. PAL provides a platform for peer interaction, which promotes mutual learning and skill development. In resource-constrained settings such as the University of Maiduguri, PAL is particularly valuable in bridging the gap caused by limited teaching staff and inadequate practical facilities.

PAL as creating a more comfortable and less intimidating environment for asking questions compared to the traditional classroom ($p < .001$). There is also a statistically significant preference for PAL as a more effective learning method ($p = .001$), indicating that this perception reflects a genuine majority view rather than chance variation. At the same time, students significantly acknowledge that traditional lectures provide greater structure ($p < .001$), affirming the continued relevance of the conventional teaching approach. PAL is further recognised as more flexible and student-friendly ($p < .001$), highlighting its distinctive advantage in supporting student engagement. Most importantly, the statistically significant agreement that PAL and traditional teaching complement each other ($p < .001$) suggests strong support for a blended instructional model. Finally, PAL offers important benefits in comfort, flexibility, and perceived learning effectiveness, students value the structured nature of traditional lectures, advocating for an integrated approach that combines the strengths of both methods.

REFERENCES

- AlShareef, S. M., Aldayel, A. Y., Alghamdi, H. M., Alosaimi, M. B., Alharbi, M. M., Aldayel, A. A., & Alhussain, H. A. (2019). Perceptions on reciprocal peer teaching among medical students as learners and as Tutors;. *Advances in Medical Education and Practice*, 10, 817-827. <https://doi.org/10.2147/amep.s220728>
- Bandura, A. (1986) *Social Foundations of Thought and Action: A Social Cognitive Theory*. Prentice-Hall.
- Brierley, C., Ellis, L. and Reid, E.R. (2022) Peer-assisted learning in medical education: A systematic review and meta-analysis, *Medical Education*, 56(4), pp. 365–373. <https://doi.org/10.1111/medu.14672>
- Burgess, A., McGregor, D., & Mellis, C. (2014). Medical students as peer tutors: A systematic review. *BMC Medical Education*, 14(1), 2-8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6920-14-115>

- Chiegeiro, C. V., Anarado, A., Phoebe, O. N., Ijeoma, O., Victoria, I. C., Njideka, I. P., & Stephanie, O. C. (2025). Peer teaching on students performance in anatomy in college of nursing sciences University of Nigeria teaching hospital, Enugu. *African Journal of Biomedical Research*, 28(4), 276-285. <https://doi.org/10.53555/ajbr.v28i4s.8490>
- Collins, A., Brown, J. S., & Newman, S. E. (2018). Cognitive apprenticeship: Teaching the crafts of reading, writing, and mathematics. *Knowing, Learning, and Instruction*, 453-494. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315044408-14>
- Cornock, C. and McKenna, L. (2012) Crossing professional barriers with peer-assisted learning, *Nurse Education Today*, 32(7), pp. 728–733. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2012.05.008>
- Elshami, W., Abuzaid, M., & Abdalla, M. (2020). Radiography students' perceptions of peer assisted learning. *Radiography*, 26(2), e109-e113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radi.2019.12.002>
- Engels, D., Haupt, C., Kugelmann, D., & Dethleffsen, K. (2021). The peer teachers' perception of intrinsic motivation and rewards. *Advances in Physiology Education*, 45(4), 758-768. <https://doi.org/10.1152/advan.00023.2021>
- Feng, H., Luo, Z., Wu, Z., & Li, X. (2024). Effectiveness of peer-assisted learning in health professional education: A scoping review of systematic reviews. *BMC Medical Education*, 24(1), 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-024-06434-7>
- Jawhari, A. A., Safhi, M. A., Magadmi, M. M., Alobaidi, R. H., Alghamdi, K. M., Basyouni, R. N., Saggaf, O. M., Yasawy, M. A., & Magadmi, R. M. (2021). Effect of peer-assisted learning on enhancing clinical research skills among medical students: Students' and tutors' perceptions. *Advances in Medical Education and Practice*, 12, 685-695. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-279191/v1>
- Johnson, D. W., Johnson, R. T., & Smith, K. A. (1998). Cooperative learning returns to college what evidence is there that it works? *Change: The Magazine of Higher Learning*, 30(4), 26-35. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00091389809602629>
- Kassab, S.E., Abu-Hijleh, M.F., Al-Shboul, Q. and Hamdy, H. (2006) Peer tutoring improves student performance in problem-based learning, *Medical Education*, 40(9), pp. 832–839.
- Lincoln, M. A., & McAllister, L. L. (1993). Peer learning in clinical education. *Medical teacher*, 15(1), 17-26.
- Loke, A. J., & Chow, F. L. (2007). Learning partnership—the experience of peer tutoring among nursing students: A qualitative study. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, 44(2), 237-244. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2005.11.028>
- Markowski, M., Bower, H., Essex, R., & Yearley, C. (2021). Peer learning and collaborative placement models in health care: A systematic review and qualitative synthesis of the literature. *Journal of Clinical Nursing*, 30(11-12), 1519-1541. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jocn.15661>
- Meertens, R. (2016). Utilisation of a peer assisted learning scheme in an undergraduate diagnostic radiography module. *Radiography*, 22(1), e69-e74. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radi.2015.08.004>
- Nestel, D. and Kidd, J. (2005) Peer tutoring in patient-centred interviewing skills: Experience of a project for first-year students, *Medical Teacher*, 27(5), pp. 439–444.
- Oppong, E. D., Kwakye, S. K., Kumi, R., & Quartey, J. (2024). Perceptions of Allied health students about lecture and peer-assisted learning. *African Journal of Health Professions Education*, e1564. <https://doi.org/10.7196/ajhpe.2024.v16i3.1564>
- Piaget, J. (1950) *The Psychology of Intelligence*. London: Routledge and Kegan Paul.
- Røe, Y., Johansen, T. S., & Brusset, E. B. (2025). Empowering digital competence through peer-assisted learning and virtual reality in health professions education. *Frontiers in Education*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2025.1550396>
- Ross, M. T., & Cameron, H. S. (2007). Peer assisted learning: A planning and implementation framework: AMEE guide No. 30. *Medical Teacher*, 29(6), 527-545. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01421590701665886>

- Secomb, J. (2008). A systematic review of peer teaching and learning in clinical education. *Journal of Clinical Nursing*, 17(6), 703-716. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2702.2007.01954.x>
- Ten Cate, O., & Durning, S. (2007). Peer teaching in medical education: Twelve reasons to move from theory to practice. *Medical Teacher*, 29(6), 591-599. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01421590701606799>
- Topping, K. J. (1996). The effectiveness of peer tutoring in further and higher education: A typology and review of the literature. *Higher Education*, 32(3), 321-345. <https://doi.org/10.1007/bf00138870>
- Topping, K. J. (2005). Trends in peer learning. *Educational psychology*, 25(6), 631-645.
- Trowler, V. (2010) Student engagement literature review. York: Higher Education Academy.
- Vermunt, J. D., & Verloop, N. (1999). Congruence and friction between learning and teaching. *Learning and Instruction*, 9(3), 257-280. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0959-4752\(98\)00028-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0959-4752(98)00028-0)
- Vygotsky, L.S. (1978) *Mind in Society: The Development of Higher Psychological Processes*. Harvard University Press.
- Williams, B., & Fowler, J. (2014). Can near-peer teaching improve academic performance? *International Journal of Higher Education*, 3(4). <https://doi.org/10.5430/ijhe.v3n4p142>
- Williams, C. A., Vidal, T., Carletti, P., Rizvi, A., & Tolchinsky, C. A. (2021). Peer-assisted learning (PAL): Perceptions and wellness of first-year medical students. *Medical Science Educator*, 31(6), 1911-1918. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40670-021-01381-0>